

INDIRECT QUANTIFICATION OF DAMAGE GROWTH DURING THREE-POINT BEND FATIGUE OF GFRP SPECIMENS

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ABSTRACT

A zone of fibre breaks, matrix cracking and splitting is observed to grow in both length and depth from the tensile surface of GFRP rods and laminates during cyclic three-point bending. The damage length and depth do not increase at the same rate during a fatigue test and any relation that might exist between them under one set of loading conditions does not necessarily hold under other loading conditions. If no relation exists between the two damage dimensions for a range of load ratios there must be at least two measured parameters to fully characterize the damage. The measured parameters must have a differing sensitivity to each damage dimension. Bending stiffness, acoustic emission and attenuation of an acoustic signal have each been explored as indicators of damage length and depth in unidirectional pultruded rods and cross-ply laminates at various load ratios.

INTRODUCTION

The objective of this work is to measure indirectly the growth of damage in GFRP rods and laminates in the length and depth directions during three-point bend fatigue. Although it is possible to make accurate visual measurements of the damage state at regular intervals during a laboratory fatigue test, visual measurements often cannot be made in practice where components are not accessible. Also, some tests continue for extended periods of time and recording visual measurements is impractical.

The following three parameters have shown promise in determining the damage state in this work :

- reduction in bending stiffness
- source location of acoustic emission events
- attenuation of an acoustic signal

Bending stiffness is defined as the initial slope of the load versus centre span deflection curve. As the damage grows during cycling the bending stiffness decreases as a direct result of increasing damage length and depth.

An acoustic emission is the generation of a transient elastic wave by a rapid release of strain energy from a localized source within the material. Emissions may be generated by matrix cracking and splitting, delamination, fibre breakage, pullout and friction between fracture surfaces [1]. These emissions are detected and recorded as acoustic emission events continuously throughout the test. Various waveform parameters are associated with each event as well as the location from which the event was generated. After post-test data filtering to eliminate events not associated with the crack front, the maximum extent of event locations along the length of the specimens indicates the damage length.

An acoustic signal is *attenuated* when the waveform parameters associated with it are reduced in magnitude as the signal propagates. Cycling is halted briefly while simulated (and repeatable) AE signals are "pulsed" from one end of the specimen through the damage zone and received at the opposing end. The amount of attenuation provides an indication of the damage state.

The precision with which the damage state is determined depends on the sensitivity of the above three parameters to each damage dimension. Bending stiffness reduction, acoustic emission, acoustic attenuation and direct visual measurements have been recorded for each of twelve samples. The usefulness of each measured parameter in monitoring the damage dimensions is determined by comparison with the visual measurements.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Figure 1 shows the three-point bend geometry, with damage length $2a$ and damage depth d shown schematically. Of the twelve samples tested five were unidirectional glass fibre/polyester rods, four were unidirectional glass fibre/epoxy rods and three were glass fibre/polyester cross-ply laminates. The rods were all of circular cross section, 16 mm in diameter. The laminates were 40 mm wide and 15 mm deep with a $[(0/90)4/0]_T$ stacking sequence, where the plies are of different thickness as shown in Figure 1(c). For all specimens the span was 480 mm. The minimum span to depth ratio was therefore 30:1 so that shear deflections were minimal [2]. Three different load ratios were used as summarized in Table 1.

All samples were tested in an MTS servohydraulic fatigue machine under computer control. The load was cycled at a frequency of approximately 0.3 Hz. The maximum loads were approximately 80% of the breaking strength for each of the samples as determined from a routine static test; the minimum loads can be determined from the load ratio.

Bending stiffness measurements were made by interrupting the fatigue test automatically, unloading the sample and reloading slowly to a predetermined load, during which the centre deflection was measured and recorded by the computer. These measurements were taken at roughly 200 cycle intervals in all the tests, with an average of 25 readings per test.

Acoustic emissions were recorded with a PAC 3400 AE analyzer in two channel mode with a PAC R15-F transducer attached to each end of the specimen being tested. All events on both channels were recorded at 40 dB preamplification, 0.1V threshold and 100 μ s dead time. The amplification and threshold voltage settings were such that no events below 60 dB were recorded. In addition to the location of each event, the amplitude, duration, energy, counts and load at which an event occurred were recorded.

At the same time as the bending stiffness measurements, a simulated AE signal was pulsed through the specimen by a third R15-F transducer attached next to channel one. The "pulser" output is recorded on both channels one and two. For

Figure 1. (a) 3-point bend geometry. (b) Cross section of unidirectional rod. (c) Cross section of [(0/90)₄/0] laminate.

TABLE 1

Test Samples

Sample	Type	Matrix	Load Ratio	Sample	Type	Matrix	Load Ratio
A	rod	poly.	0.10	G	rod	epoxy	0.17
B	rod	poly.	0.10	H	rod	epoxy	0.45
C	rod	poly.	0.10	I	rod	epoxy	0.45
D	rod	poly.	0.17	J	lam.	poly.	0.30
E	rod	poly.	0.45	K	lam.	poly.	0.30
F	rod	epoxy	0.17	L	lam.	poly.	0.10

both channels the amplitude, duration, energy and counts of the simulated signal were recorded. Also, the time taken by the signal to travel from channel one to channel two was recorded. All attenuation measurements were made with a small (1-2 lb.) load applied to the sample.

Direct visual measurements of damage length and depth were made at the same time cycling was interrupted for bending stiffness and attenuation measurements. The lengths ranged from 0 to 300 mm and were simple to measure. The depths, however, ranged from 0 to 4 mm which required more careful measurement. For the circular cross section rods the damage width at the centre of the span was measured from which the depth was calculated. For the laminates a travelling microscope was used to measure the depth directly.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Unidirectional Rods

A strength of materials approach is used to calculate the bending stiffness. Since the fibres are unidirectional an isotropic solution is adequate to describe the deflection due to bending. Because the span to depth ratio is fairly high at 30:1, deflections due to shear are neglected. For brevity the derivation is not included here [3]. The rod is analyzed as a cantilever beam by considering only the right half. Accordingly, the inverse of the bending stiffness is

$$\frac{v}{p} = \frac{1}{3E} \left[\frac{(L-a)^3}{I_1} + \frac{3La^2 - 3L^2a + a^3}{I_2} \right] \quad (1)$$

where I_1 and I_2 are the area moments of inertia of the undamaged and damaged cross sections, Figure 1(b). In the undamaged state both a and d are zero and equation (1) reduces to the well known cantilever beam equation.

Using equation (1) the bending stiffness can be predicted by substituting for measured values of a and d , and compared with the measured values. Figure 2 shows data for polyester rods A, B and C, all at a load ratio 0.10. The straight line represents ideal agreement between the calculated and measured bending stiffness. Figure 3 shows similar data for rods D, F and G at a load ratio of 0.17, with fairly good agreement. Figure 4 shows data for rods E, H and I at a load ratio 0.45. The fit is reasonable, but not as good as the previous ones, with the predicted values consistently lower than the measured values. Examination of these samples after testing showed that the assumption of only two damage parameters is not entirely accurate. Equation (1) assumes that the depth d is constant along the entire damage length a . For the samples tested at the higher load ratio, the damage depth decreased slightly towards the longitudinal extremes. As the maximum depth d is the value used in equation (1), the predicted bending stiffness will be an underestimate.

Acoustic emission source location can be determined using two transducers, based on the difference in arrival times of a given event at the two sensors. The travel times can be converted to distances by measuring the wave speed independently. The method of location based on travel time is potentially very accurate [4]. However, for reasons to be discussed below a number of factors cause events to be located erroneously. In particular, events can appear to be located, and perhaps even generated, outside the damage zone. Therefore it is necessary to

Figure 2. Comparison between normalized bending stiffness measured directly and predicted from equation (1) for rods A, B and C at load ratio 0.10.

Figure 3. Comparison between normalized bending stiffness measured directly and predicted from equation (1) for rods D, F and G at load ratio 0.17.

Figure 4. Comparison between normalized bending stiffness measured directly and predicted from equation (1) for rods E, H and I at load ratio 0.45.

discriminate between events detected as being inside the damage length and those detected as being outside the damage length.

Figure 5(d) is an events versus location histogram over the interval $2600 < N < 2700$ for sample G. The distance between the two peaks is 214 mm, compared to the visually measured damage length of 223 mm. The AE event parameters of the events generated at these peaks were isolated from the rest of the AE data and used to define criteria to differentiate between events generated at the two advancing crack fronts and those generated elsewhere. The waveform parameters are the event amplitude, duration, counts and energy. After an event by event comparison, it was observed that all events located at the peaks had the characteristics shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Characteristics of events located near crack fronts, rod G.

	channel closest to peak	channel farthest from peak
duration (us)	54-237	> 0
energy	4-50	> 0
counts		> 0
amplitude (dB)	68-78	64-71

Figure 5. Events vs. location histograms for rod G for increasing cycles, N.

The remaining data were filtered, excluding all events that did not meet the first three of the above four criteria (the majority of events fell within the amplitude range), and plotted as a function of increasing number of cycles in Figure 5. The locations of filtered events spread outwards with increasing cycles, indicating growth of damage in the length direction. The exact length of damage, however, is consistently overestimated (Figure 6). According to Hamstad [5], the accuracy of source location by first penetration of the threshold suffers from attenuation of the first half-cycle of the AE wave before it hits the farthest sensor. This has the effect of locating the source nearer to the nearest sensor than it actually is (by overestimating the time taken by the wave to reach the farthest sensor). Consequently, the damage length is overestimated.

Attenuation of an acoustic signal may provide a third indication of the damage state. A series of simulated AE events are pulsed through the sample by attaching a third, active, transducer to the specimen and forcing an acoustic wave from one end of the rod to the other. By placing this "pulsar" at one end of the rod, adjacent to channel one, and pulsing a signal past the damage zone to channel two, any difference in waveform parameters at channels one and two may give some indication of the damage state.

Important considerations are the positioning of the pulsar and transducers, the AE threshold and the waveform parameters to be monitored. Previous work using a pulsar and a single transducer on polyester rods [6] has shown that the AE energy transmitted decreases as damage grows (Figure 7). Results of subsequent tests with one pulsar and two transducers are presented in Table 3.

TABLE 3

Effect of transducer position and AE threshold on AE energy transmitted.

Specimen	T/D Position	AE Threshold	Effect on Energy Transmitted
A, C, D, E	end	71	15% reduction at d=2 mm
F	compressive	51	no change
G	end	60	75% reduction at d=2 mm
H	compressive	60	no change
I	tensile	51	no change

It can be seen that the acoustic energy is attenuated only when the pulsar and receiving transducer are on the ends of the rods, but not when they are on the tensile or compressive surfaces. Figure 8 shows the energy transmitted as a function of depth, with the transducers on the ends and the AE threshold set at 60 dB (rod G), and with the transducers on the tension surface and the AE threshold set at 51 dB (rod I). The trend for rod G is similar to that shown in Figure 7. The difference in degree of attenuation between Figures 7 and 8 may be due to two reasons: rods A and B have a polyester matrix whilst rod I has an epoxy matrix and the AE thresholds are different. A practical application of this technique would require a calibration of the material to be monitored.

Figure 6. Comparison between damage length measured directly and measured by AE source location for rod G.

Figure 7. Attenuation of acoustic energy as a function of damage depth for rods A and C.

Figure 8. Attenuation of acoustic energy as a function of damage depth for rods G and I.

Cross-ply Laminates

Preliminary results for three identical laminates are presented. Some experimental difficulties were encountered, as the laminates are of sufficient thickness to allow growth through the depth, which leads to considerable loads being applied. Too high a load causes the sample to fail catastrophically, either following degradation of the bottom ply or by crushing under the central load point. Conversely, too low a load leads to a formidable amount of AE data being gathered. The first sample tested successfully was cycled at a load ratio of 0.30. Damage initiated after approximately 11000 cycles on the tensile surface at one edge. After a further 1000 cycles the damage grew across the tensile surface from edge to edge and in the length direction. Further cycling caused the sample to crush beneath the central load point followed closely by complete failure. The second and third successful samples, K and L, were cycled at slightly lower loads with damage in the depth direction initiated intentionally as described below. Tests carried out on numerous samples without instrumentation have shown that damage will propagate at lower loads where crushing does not occur, but at a very slow rate. By inducing damage artificially excessively long tests were avoided in the present work.

A more complex analysis is required to predict the bending stiffness of the laminates than for the rods. The complete derivation is excluded for brevity. From

simple beam theory and classical laminated plate theory (LPT) it can be shown that the bending stiffness relation for the laminates is the same as equation (1) by replacing $1/EI$ with D'_{11}/b where D'_{11} is calculated from LPT and depends on stacking sequence and material properties and b is the laminate width [7]. Thus

$$\frac{v}{p} = \frac{1}{3b} [{}_1D'_{11} (L-a)^3 + {}_2D'_{11} (3La^2 - 3L^2a + a^3)] \quad (2)$$

where ${}_1D'_{11}$ and ${}_2D'_{11}$ are for the damaged and undamaged cross sections.

Figure 9 shows the relation between bending stiffness evaluated by substituting observed damage depth and length values in equation (2), and measured values. Damage in laminate K began with crushing beneath the load point early in the test. Rather than discontinue the test, the specimen was turned over such that the crushing damage was on the tension side. Data in Figure 9 from laminate K correspond to subsequent growth. The remaining points are from laminate L. For this test the initiation phase was overlooked in favor of monitoring growth. A shallow notch was made with a jeweler's saw on the tension side directly beneath the load point. The notch was deepened at approximately 50 cycle intervals up to 400 cycles. This allowed the depth to be measured very accurately and avoided generation of excessive AE data. The agreement between theory and experiment in Figure 9 is fair considering the assumptions made in determining the quantity D'_{11} . In particular D'_{11} depends on individual ply properties which are somewhat idealized for the analysis.

Figure 9. Comparison between normalized bending stiffness measured directly and predicted from equation (2) for laminates K and L.

Figure 10. (a-e) Events vs location histograms for laminate L for increasing cycles, N. (f) Comparison between damage length measured directly and measured by AE source location for laminate L.

AE source location was performed for laminate L with the transducers attached to the ends, Figure 10. A notable increase in signal travel time was observed as the damage progressed beyond 60 mm in length and 3 mm in depth. Since source location depends on signal travel time, this increase must be taken into account. As with the rods, source location overestimates the damage length (Figure 10(f)) and further work is needed to improve accuracy.

Attenuation measurements were made using the same procedure as for the rods. For laminate K the sensors were mounted on the compression surface and for laminate L the sensors were mounted on the ends. The signal travel time and transmitted AE energy for laminate K remained nearly constant. Figure 11 shows a travel time increase and energy attenuation of the pulsed signal for laminate L. Of all twelve samples this was the only one that showed a noticeable travel time increase. Whether this was due to the sensor position or to the extreme damage state was not determined, though laminate L was badly damaged (Figure 9 shows a bending stiffness reduction of 70% at this stage, the lowest of all samples). According to Mitchell and Miller [8] the travel time increase may result from a longer distance travelled by the wave as it passes through the damage. However, the effect may also be due to attenuation of the first part of the wave, making the travel time longer, with path and speed unchanged.

Figure 11. Attenuation of acoustic energy and increase in travel time as a function of damage depth for laminate L.

CONCLUSIONS

Damage during cyclic bending of GFRP rods and laminates grows in length and depth from beneath the central load point of three-point bend specimens. For unidirectional rods the depth d is approximately constant over the length $2a$ for load ratios 0.10 and 0.17, but decreases outwards from the centre for load ratio 0.45. For cross-ply laminates the depth is constant for the entire damage length for load ratios 0.10 and 0.30.

Simple beam theory is adequate to describe the bending stiffness of damaged unidirectional rods yielding one equation with two unknowns, a and d . Laminated plate theory is adequate to describe the bending stiffness of damaged cross-ply laminates yielding a similar equation, also with unknowns a and d .

Acoustic emission monitoring, after suitable data filtering, locates events generated along the damaged length of rods and laminates during cycling. The extent of the events on an events versus location histogram is a direct measure of the damage length, $2a$.

Attenuation of an acoustic signal gives an indication of the damage depth d when a simulated AE source is transmitted and received by transducers mounted perpendicular to the specimen's longitudinal axis. The AE energy transmitted decreases as damage grows through the depth, but is a function of material and AE threshold settings.

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